

MICROSTRUCTURES AND MECHANICAL PROPERTIES OF SILICON-CARBIDE FIBER

REINFORCED ALUMINUM COMPOSITE MATERIALS AND THEIR PREFORM WIRES*

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Silicon-carbide (SiC) is considered to be one of the most promising candidates for reinforcements. This study is focused on multifilament yarn fibers of SiC and their potential for the application to fiber reinforced aluminum alloy matrix composite materials is investigated. Test materials were made by hot-press method and their mechanical properties and microstructures with the special emphasis on interfacial structures were inspected. Microstructural and microchemical analysis were carried out by means of transmission electron microscopy (TEM) with the aids of EDXA. The dominant factors which reduce the strength of composite material were found to be degradation of fibers, interfacial phase formation, cavity formation in the matrix and along fibers and others. Based on the result obtained, pure aluminum is selected as matrix and with proper modification in the fabrication process it becomes possible to produce preform wires with their average strength higher than 1.2 GPa.

Introduction

Silicon carbide (SiC) is known to be one of the most promising candidates for reinforcements because of its high intrinsic strength, high temperature strength, stiffness and high temperature stability(1). As well as their potential for the use in composite materials, it is considered to be one of the candidates for fusion reactor materials because of its resistance to radiation damage, resistance to thermal shock and low activation characteristics(2).

The recent development of SiC as fiber reinforcement can be divided into three trends:

- 1) production of SiC monofilaments by chemical vapour deposition(CVD).
- 2) production of relatively inexpensive SiC whiskers.
- 3) production of multifilament SiC yarn from a spun polymer precursor.

The successful production of multifilament-yarn fibers obtained from a spun polymer precursor was first reported by S. Yajima and coworkers(3) and its development to commercial plant has been effected by Nippon Carbon Co..

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The commercial production of fibers, in the form of continuous yarn of 500 fibers, started in 1981 under the trade name of Nicalon(4).

This work is carried out with the basis of the recent extensive advancement in fabrication processes of Nicalon fiber and its preform wire in an aluminum matrix.

The objectives of this investigation are to get the fundamental understandings of SiC fiber reinforcement in multifilament-yarn continuous fiber (Nicalon) reinforced composite materials with aluminum alloy matrices and to establish fabrication process of aluminum matrix preform wire for use in a commercial plant(5).

This paper is divided into two parts. The first part presents the microstructures and mechanical properties of SiC/Al alloy composite materials made by the liquid metal pressing method and of aluminum matrix preform wire with special emphasis on interfacial structures. The second part presents successful improvement of mechanical properties for the modified SiC/Al preform wires.

Experimental Procedure

The fiber reinforced metal (FRM) plates tested were made by the liquid metal pressing method (hot press) using unidirectionally aligned prepreg sheets of SiC fibers and sheets of matrix materials. The chemical composition of matrix materials used is shown in Table.I. Mechanical properties of the composite materials, the SiC fibers and the matrix materials were measured by tensile testing. Strain rates for the test were within the range of 8.3×10^{-4} /sec. and 1.6×10^{-6} /sec. Microstructures of composite materials were inspected by means of transmission electron microscopy (TEM). The microchemical analysis were carried out with energy dispersive X-ray analysis (EDXA). The macrostructure and fracture surface analysis were done by scanning electron microscopy (SEM). Fiber volume fraction of FRMs and size distribution of SiC fibers were quantitatively analyzed from the SEM pictures using micro-computer system(6). The same inspections were done for SiC/Al(A1050) preform wires.

Table I. Chemical Composition of Matrix Materials Used(wt.%)

Mark	Si	Fe	Cu	Mn	Mg	Cr	Zn	Ti	Ni	Al
A1050	0.25	0.40	0.05	0.05	0.05	-	0.05	0.03	-	bal.
A5052	0.25	-	0.10	0.10	2.6	0.25	0.10	-	-	bal.
A6061	0.60	0.70	0.30	0.15	1.0	0.20	0.25	0.15	-	bal.
AZ91C	0.30	-	0.10	0.13	bal.	-	0.80	-	0.01	9.0

Mechanical Properties

The tensile test results of hot pressed materials and preform wires are shown in Table II. In the table, estimated rule of mixture (ROM) values for tensile stress, σ_t (ROM), were obtained from simple rule of mixture using fiber strength of 3.0 GPa. Only for the case of SiC/A-1050, average tensile stress reached to higher than 60 % of the ROM value. Rest of the plate specimens fabricated by hot press showed low tensile stress lower than 30 % of the ROM values. The results of the preform wires have a wide scatter band of 80 MPa with the average tensile stress close to those of SiC/A-1050 plate specimens. Although the plate specimens have slight strain rate dependence of tensile stress, the tensile stress of preform wire looses about 5 % of the stress by reducing strain rate from 10^{-5} /sec. to 10^{-6} /sec.. At the lowest strain rate of 10^{-6} /sec., individual fractures of reinforcing

Table II. Results of Tensile Test

MATRIX	SHAPE	FABRICATION METHOD	FIBER VOLUME FRACTION	TENSILE STRESS (σ_t :Mpa)	$\frac{\sigma_t (EXP)}{\sigma_t (ROM)}$
A-1050	plate	hot press	0.34	630	0.67
A-5052	plate	hot press	0.31	251	0.26
A-6061	plate	hot press	0.42	313	0.26
AZ91C	plate	hot press	0.37	162	0.15
A-1050	wire	infiltration	0.41	673	0.58

fibers could be detected from the early part of a work hardening stage. This is a clear evidence that the fibers embedded into the matrix were not perfectly aligned. The improvement of fiber alignment would raise the tensile stress of the FRM. Together with the tensile stress measurements of a bundle of 500 fibers, a single yarn of fibers, the tensile stress of monofilaments (individual fibers) were tested and those were investigated as a function of fiber diameter. Statistically, fiber strength increased with decreasing fiber diameter and the average strength of extracted fibers from preform wires was reduced about 15 % of the average strength of the fibers prior to the preform wire fabrication. This means that the degradation of fiber strength during the fabrication of FRMs, about 17 % of the strength prior to the fabrication, was mainly come from the structural evolution by thermo-mechanical history.

Macrostructure of FRMs

The cross sectional view of SiC/Al(A-1050) plate in transverse direction to SiC fibers is shown in Photo.1. Although there remains the

Photo.1 Cross Sectional View of SiC/Al(A-1050) Sheet Made by Hot Press.

traces of lamination and those of SiC yarn (500 fibers/yarn), the fibers are dispersed fairly uniform manner. The characteristic feature of macrostructure is the formation of cavities in the matrix, dominantly in the region with low volume fraction of fibers. The size distributions of cavities go up to a few hundred micro meters and in the cases of SiC/Al(A-6061) and SiC/Mg(AZ91C), the cavity formation was significant.

The observations by means of scanning electron microscopy provide that wettabilities of matrix materials to SiC fibers are excellent. These results would suggest that suppressions of cavity formation in the matrix and of low fiber volume fraction region are important problems to be solved.

Fracture Surfaces of FRMs

The SEM fractographs of FRM plates with Al alloy matrices provide a typical origin of fracture initiation. That is the crack initiation around cavities which was most significant in A-6061 matrix. The size of the cavities could be relatively related to fracture stress and with decreasing cavity sizes fracture stress was increased. Photo.2 shows a typical fracture surface of SiC/Al(A-6061). In general, cellular dendritic structures were observed at the cavity surfaces which means those cavities would be a kind of shrinkage cavity. Those solidification cells were perpendicular to the fiber axis and, in most of all cases, cell boundaries acted as fracture initiation of fibers. This tendency may suggest us that those cell boundaries induce stress concentration and also induce fiber degradations, because these positions are most favourable to be produced brittle phases.

Stress-strain curves of tensile test and SEM results indicated that fibers were not definitely well aligned to a single direction and this would reduce the effect of reinforcement, although this couldn't be a major factor. In the case of SiC/Mg(AZ91C), where tensile stress was the lowest, besides the cavity formation in the matrix, formation of interfacial phases

Photo.2 Fracture Surface of SiC/Al(A-6061)

Photo.3 Fracture Surface of SiC/Mg(AZ91C)

Photo.4 Cross Sectional View of SiC/Al(A-1050) Preform Wire

between the fiber and the matrix was observed. Photo.3 shows typical structures in SiC/Mg(AZ91C). The thickness of the interfacial layer is the order of 1 μm .

Fracture surfaces of the preform wires were almost identical to those of hot pressed materials with Al(A-1050) matrix. A cross sectional view of the preform wire is shown in Photo.4. In the center of fibers, there generally existed large cavities prolonged to the fiber axis and further there were small shrinkage cavities and bubbles in the matrix. Again, the preform wires with large cavities presented lower tensile stress than those with less porosity.

Observation of Microstructure by TEM

Transmission Electron Microscopic Analysis

Microstructural investigations by means of high resolution transmission electron microscopy were carried out using JEM-200CX with 200 KV accelerating voltage. Interfacial structure of SiC/Al(A-1050) plate was quite sound and no precipitates nor micro cavities were detected as shown in Photo. 5. As far as we inspected by electron diffraction pattern (EDP) analysis, SiC fibers were not crystalline but amorphous and a small extent of crystal growth from Fiber side to matrix side was observed. An example is shown in Photo 5 as indicated with an arrow. The crystal grain size of the Al matrix was the smallest at interface and with increasing the distance from interfaces, the size of grain was increased. From the structure of dislocations, interfacial stresspile up is considered to be negligibly small. The wavy structure of the interface with some small extruding SiC crystals from fiber side seems to indicate that there are not only physical and chemical bondings but also strong mechanical bonding between fiber and matrix. In the case of SiC/Al(A-5052), precipitation along fiber-matrix

Photo.5 Matrix-fiber interface of SiC/Al(A-1050) Plate (region A and B corresponds Al and SiC, respectively. and arrow indicates SiC crystal growth from SiC fiber)

Photo.6 Matrix-fiber interface of SiC/Al(A-5052)
 (diffraction pattern (1), (2) and (3) corresponds
 A;Al, B;precipitates and C; amorphous SiC)

interface was observed. Photo. 6 shows an example, where region A, B and C correspond Al matrix, interface and SiC fiber, respectively. From EDP analysis, SiC fibers were mostly amorphous state. The EDPs from region A and B were taken with different specimen tilting condition but the analysis provided that those precipitates were Al_4C_3 . We have had some different EDPs at the interface and those were yet to be identified. Dislocation density in the matrix was higher than that in Al(A-1050) matrix but any significant dislocation pile up at the interface was not observed. In the case of SiC/Al(A-6061), the precipitation at interface was very similar to that in SiC/Al(A-5052), but an additional feature of dislocation pile up in the triangular region at the interface was also observed. This structure was related to the solidification structure. Therefore, this is interpreted to act to concentrate stress and to induce low stress failure of the FRM.

As shown in Photo.3, magnesium alloy matrix (AZ91C) produced thick interfacial layer which acted as the fracture initiator. TEM inspection results of the interfacial layer are shown in Photo.7. The interfacial layer was about the thickness of 1 μm . Although SEM images show a clear separation of the layer from the matrix, TEM images show not a drastic but a transitional change of microstructure. As shown in Photo.7 (a) and (b), interface layer has a fibrous carbide structure with their axis perpendicular to the interface. Although a definite EDP analysis is yet to be done, the interfacial layer seems to be a kind of eutectic structure. Outside of the fibrous structure, the size of carbide phase becomes smaller with increasing the distance from the interface and they change their shapes from fibrous to acicular, as shown in Photo.7 (c). In this system, suppression of interface layer formation should be the prime problem to be solved.

Photo.7 Microstructures of SiC/Mg(AZ91C)
 ((1);Bright field image, (2)Dark field image of area (1) with carbide spot and (3);Dark field image of carbide from the outer region of interface layer.)

Energy Dispersive X-ray Analysis

The SiC/Al(A-1050) plate did not show any kind of micro-segregation across the interface and micro-segregation of Fe was observed locally regardless of fiber-matrix interface, rather randomly in the matrix. But in the case of SiC/Al(A-6061), micro-segregation of Fe at the interface was observed and no other segregation was detected. In the case of SiC/Al(A-5052), micro-segregation of magnesium at the interface was clearly observed, as shown in Fig.1. Because our EDXA system cannot provide informations of very important light elements, such as C, N and O, we cannot make a clear understanding of the effects of micro-segregation at the interface on strength of FRM. Nevertheless, the micro-segregation of Mg would indicate the formation of MgO at the interface and such reaction would affect the strength of fiber and interface.

Characteristics of Preform Wires

The above mentioned results, obtained in this work, indicate that the strength of SiC fibers and the fiber-matrix interfacial structures are the most important factors. As to the former, thermally and chemically induced degradations of fibers are estimated to be dominantly due to the crystallization of amorphous SiC and crystal growth from the fiber surface. The latter can be understood by the carbide formations (Al_4C_3 etc.) at the interface and the solidification structure at the interface which act as the initiation site for fracture. Under optimum condition, we could obtain average tensile stress of 800 MPa for SiC/Al(A-1050) composite materials

Fig.1

Concentration Profile of Al and Mg near interface in SiC/Al(A-5052), indicating Mg enrichment at the interface.

with 34 % fiber volume fraction. In the cases of other matrix materials, their strength were lower than in the case of Al(A-1050) matrix and these can be understood through the microstructures.

The A-1050 aluminum alloy has been selected as the matrix and with proper modification in the fabrication process, it has become possible to obtain stronger preform wires than those by the original process. Figure 2 shows the tensile test results of preform-wires. Those preform wires include single yarn of SiC fibers, that is 500 SiC fibers, and the only difference is the thermo-mechanical history during the fabrication process. The solid line in the figure is calculated from the simple rule of mixture using the fiber strength of 3.0 GPa. The filled mark in the figure indicates the average strengths of preform wires by the original process. The preform wires produced by the modified process, indicated with blank marks, showed higher tensile stress, about 100 - 300 MPa higher, than that of the preform wires by the original process even with the same fiber volume fraction. This improvement would come from the reduction of the degradation of fiber strength during the fabrication process. As to the accomplishment ratio of wire strength to the theoretical value from simple rule of mixture; $\sigma_t(\text{EXP})/\sigma_t(\text{ROM})$, the values about 0.6 to 0.7 at the original process has improved to be above 0.8. In our modified process, the fiber volume fraction larger than 50 % is realized and with the fiber volume fraction larger than 35 %, the accomplishment ratio becomes to unity.

Each preform wires were inspected to correlate their strength and fracture behavior. The objective is to find out the key factors to attain the accomplishment ratio to the unity, that is to reach to the theoretical strength of the FRM. Photo.8 is the fracture surface of the high strength preform wire with its tensile stress of 1.3 GPa. The SiC fibers were uniformly embedded into the matrix and few cavities were observed.

Fig.2 Dependence of Tensile Stress on Size of Preform Wire. (filled mark and blank marks indicate wire fabrication process of the original and the modified, respectively. The shapes of marks represent difference of production lot.)

Photo.8 Fracture Surface of High Strength Preform Wire of SiC/Al(A-1050)

Photo.9 Fracture Surface of High Strength Preform Wire, SiC/Al(A-1050)

Comparing with the cross sectional view of the wire made by the original process, as shown in Photo.4, extensive improvements from the macroscopic point of view can be easily found out.

From the Fig.2, we could see a relatively wide scattering of the fracture stress than those observed in individual fibers or matrix. We don't have a clear understanding of the origin of the data scattering but the lower values in the preform wires indicated as circle and square in Fig.2 can be mainly related to the microcavities observed in the wires.

The fracture surface in higher magnification is shown in Photo.9. The precise inspection of microstructures by SEM reveals that the high strength preform wire has little indication of degradation of fibers nor harmful interfacial structures.

Conclusions

Silicon carbide fiber is known to be one of the most promising candidates for reinforcements and this work is carried out with the basis of the recent extensive advancement in the fabrication process of multifilament SiC yarn from a spun polymer precursor (Nicalon).

The objectives of this investigation are to get the fundamental understandings of SiC/Al alloy composite materials from both the microstructural and the mechanical stand point of view and to establish fabrication process of preform wire for use in a commercial plant.

Mechanical test by tensile test and microstructural and microchemical analysis by TEM+EDXA are carried out.

The dominant factors which reduce the strength of FRMs are found to be degradation of fibers, interfacial phase formation, cavity formation in the matrix and fiber alignment in the matrix.

Based on the results obtained, the original fabrication of preform wire is modified to suppress the mal-factors.

The modified fabrication process makes it possible to produce preform wires with their average strength higher than 1.2 GPa.

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